

BIAXIAL FLEXURAL FATIGUE OF COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

Static and cyclic biaxial bending were applied to rectangular carbon fibre/epoxy resin laminated plates with three geometric aspect ratios and all edges clamped. Damage mechanism studies and mechanical property evaluations were carried out. It was found that various damage modes, mainly matrix cracks and delamination, could occur under about 20% of the ultimate load levels, and would develop during fatigue. The amount of damage indicated by area of damage zone was mainly dependent on the load level, but not aspect ratio. Despite their low static load bearing ability, plates with higher aspect ratio could have a higher resistance to biaxial flexural fatigue.

Keywords: Biaxial loading; Flexural fatigue; NDT; CFRP

1. INTRODUCTION

With increasingly widespread utilisation of composite materials in various engineering structural systems such as aircraft, automobiles and power plants, which are typically subjected to multiaxial/biaxial loading conditions, the behaviour of composite materials under such conditions has received a great deal of attention. A considerable amount of experimental and theoretical work is associated with tubular type specimens under various biaxial stresses. Some other research programmes have been carried out with flat cruciform specimens with biaxial loading applied to the arms. Biaxial bending of plates is also a biaxial loading situation which often exists in engineering structures, for instance wing structure, automobile body and floor panels. However, there is very limited information concerning biaxial bending of composite panels, especially biaxial bending introduced by a lateral cyclic load. The present work is an experimental study into the behaviour of rectangular CFRP composite plates subjected to biaxial bending under monotonic and cyclic lateral loads. It is hoped that this primary investigation will set a useful base for further detailed studies in order to develop a design procedure for predicting microdamage and failure induced by biaxial cyclic bending in engineering practice. The aim of this paper is to describe and discuss the experimental results obtained on some rectangular laminated plates subjected to lateral central loading with all edges clamped.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Design of the biaxial bending test jig was mainly influenced by the three-point bending test rigs of the CRAG specification. The central load indenter has a 12.5mm radius, half ball, loading end. The supporting base is a combination of two pairs of supporting rails which enable one to have biaxial bending spans of various aspect ratios. The radius of the supporting corner is 5mm. The testing plate

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is clamped with a thick metal frame onto the flat tops (10mm wide) of the supporting rails by numerous screws.

The material used was XAS/913 carbon fibre/epoxy resin composite (Ciba-Geigy) with $[0_2,90_2]_{2s}$ 16-ply stacking sequence. The basic mechanical properties of the composite material are listed in Table 1. Plate specimens were cut to three sizes, 170x70, 120x70 and 70x70mm, for testing on the biaxial jig with spans 150x50, 100x50 and 50x50mm, respectively. The aspect ratio, B, is defined as the unsupported length parallel to the surface fibre direction/the unsupported length perpendicular to the surface fibre direction. Three aspect ratios, B=3, 2 and 1 were therefore set for the above specimens, respectively. All plates were nominally 2mm thick .

Table 1 Basic Mechanical Properties of the Composite Laminate

Tensile strength	Tensile failure strain	Tensile Modulus	Poisson's ratio	Flexural strength	Flexural modulus
GPa	%	GPa	(ν_{12})	GPa	GPa
1.19±0.02	1.53±0.03	73.39±1.86	0.04±0.01	1.24±0.06	71.44±3.99

The monotonic biaxial bending tests were carried out with the loading rate about 0.1kN/sec. The frequency used in fatigue was around 4 Hz to provide the loading rate of about 50kN/sec. With sine form constant amplitude cyclic loading mode, the load ratio R, minimum load/maximum load (L_{max}/L_{min}), is set as 0.1, which keeps the load indenter always in contact with the specimens in order to eliminate any impact reaction during the fatigue test. A real time computer data acquisition system was used to monitor the changes of the deflection as a result of the cyclic loading during fatigue. Ultrasonic C-scan and X-radiography techniques were employed to assess the damage condition of the specimens.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Monotonic Tests

3.1.1. Load-deflection Curves

Typical load-deflection(L/D) curves for all three aspect ratio plates are presented in Figure 1. The large deflection effect appears on the curves when the deflection reaches approximately the thickness of the plates. Several kinks, which indicate some sudden changes in the L/D relationship as a result of occurrence and progression of damage, are visible in all curves. The first kinks, identified as the onset of first cracks in the plates, have been treated as a characteristic phenomenon for the laminated plates. The final failure of the plates happens with the loading indenter cutting through the plates.

Fig.1. Typical load-deflection curves of the static biaxial bending tests.

Results of the monotonic tests are tabulated in Table 2. The ultimate failure load(UFL) decreases and the failure deflection increases with increase of the aspect ratio. The final effective stiffness, defined as the ratio of the failure load/failure deflection, naturally decreases with increase of the aspect ratio. The initial stiffness, defined at load at deflection equal to half the thickness of the plate, 1mm, also follows this trend and falls with increasing aspect ratio. The change of both effective stiffnesses with aspect ratio implies that they are structurally related parameters (change with span of support) rather than just material related properties, such as the plate flexural rigidity defined by classical plate theory[1].Although the deflection at which the first crack happened increases with the aspect ratio, the first crack loads for all aspect ratios are about the same. This has shown that the loading level is a key factor on the damage condition of the composite plates subjected to the lateral load arrangement. It is also noted that differences in these parameters are smaller between B=2 and B=3 plates than between B=1 and B=2, which seems to suggest that beyond some point, the aspect ratio could have no significant influence on the performance of the plate subjected to biaxial flexing.

TABLE 2. Results of the monotonic biaxial bending tests

Aspect ratio (B)	Ultimate failure load kN	Ultimate failure deflection mm	First crack load kN	First crack deflection mm	Initial effective stiffness kN/mm	Final effective stiffness kN/mm
1	8.67±0.71	4.93±0.20	2.03±0.10	1.11±0.08	1.71±0.07	1.76±0.14
2	7.85±0.46	5.25±0.16	2.03±0.04	1.48±0.03	1.25±0.02	1.50±0.05
3	7.67±0.27	5.78±0.22	2.03±0.09	1.61±0.05	1.20±0.02	1.33±0.05

3.1.2. Damage Assessment

Individual plates were loaded up to several different predetermined load/deflection levels, below the final failure point, and then released to be examined by NDE methods. Figs.2a-c show the X-radiography photos of the B=2 plate, as a set of examples. Fig.2a shows the damage state of the plate unloaded immediately after the first kink in the L/D curve occurred. Although the total damage zone is relatively small, there are two main damage mechanisms, namely matrix cracks and delamination, involved. Unlike simply supported plates which could have corner damage-free zones as a result of the corner lifting effects[2], these cracks and delamination in the edge clamped plates have a tendency of growing towards the corners of the specimens with increasing load levels (Fig.2b and c). As the matrix cracks always travelled beyond the boundaries of delamination zones in the damaged plates, it is supposed that delamination started from the matrix cracks as a result of interlaminar (shear and tensile) stress concentration caused by these intraply cracks.

Fig.2. Damage detected by X-radiography on the B=2 plates subjected to different load levels: a) 2.05kN, b) 4.00kN and c) 6.00kN.

Fig.3. Projected damage areas of the edge clamped plates subjected to static loading.

The projected damage areas for all three aspect ratios were measured from C-scan results, and are plotted as functions of the load at which the damage occurred in Fig.3. The actual damage areas of the plates subjected to similar load levels are almost the same regardless the aspect ratio until the load reaches quite a high level (>4 kN). These results also show that the load level is a key factor on the damage condition.

3.2. Fatigue Tests

3.2.1. Load-Cycles Data

Serial fatigue proof tests were carried out on all three aspect ratio plates. The tests results were analysed by the two parameter Weibull distribution model:

$$P=1 - \exp[-(N/b)^m],$$

where N is specimen life, m is Weibull modulus, and b is Weibull characteristic value. In the case of the fatigue life, b is the life point with the failure probability $P=0.632$.

Fig.4. The Weibull median fatigue lives of the plates under the criteria of fatigue fracture (open symbols) and $D_{max}=3\text{mm}$ (solid symbols).

Figure 4 is a plot of the maximum fatigue load (L_{max}) as a function of logarithmic number of cycles to failure ($\log N_f$), with corresponding Weibull median lives (fatigue lives with failure probability $P=0.5$)[3] for all three aspect ratio plates under the criteria of fracture and maximum deflection (D_{max}). The $L/\log N$ curves are drawn as best fit straight lines based on the monotonic data at the first half cycle and the median fatigue lives of the Weibull distribution over the tested load levels. It can be seen that under both criteria the $L/\log N$ curves for the plates with high aspect ratios are flatter than those of the square plates. This, therefore, suggests that despite their lower static load bearing abilities, plates with higher aspect ratio appear to have higher resistance to biaxial bending fatigue. It is also clear that under both criteria, the differences of $L/\log N$ curves between $B=2$ and 3 are much

smaller than between B=1 and 2, which confirmed the suggestion from the static tests that the aspect ratio could lose its significant influence on the performance of the plates subjected to biaxial flexing at higher aspect ratios.

3.2.2. Dynamic Stiffness

Changes of dynamic stiffness, which is defined as the ratio of maximum load/maximum deflection, were monitored by the computer system during fatigue. Results of three specimens, one from each aspect ratio, which failed as a result of fatigue at about 80% of their UFL, are shown in Fig.5. The dynamic stiffness of the plates were normalized with respect to the reference initial value at the start of fatigue, and presented as functions of the proportional fatigue life N/N_f , where N is the number of cycles, and N_f the number of cycles to failure. The variations of the dynamic stiffness are dramatic. At the beginning of fatigue, within about 10% of the fatigue life time, it sharply decreased to about 80-90% of its original value. The change then flattens over about the next 80% of the life time until the final stage, which covers about the last 10% of the whole life. This distinct fast-slow-fast dynamic stiffness change, to some extent, is a reflection of degradation of the plate material. In the case of composite laminates, the rigidity of the plate is reduced by the accumulation and progression of various damage mechanisms during fatigue.

Fig.5. Changes of the dynamic stiffnesses as functions of the proportional fatigue life.

3.2.3. Residual Properties

Static residual property tests were carried out on some specimens after fatigue. The L_{max} and number of cycles were pre-determined. Residual failure load, deflection and initial stiffness were measured. However, none of these measured parameters show very clear trends, except for the initial effective stiffness in some conditions. The effect of large deflection on the plates with fatigue-induced damage could be a possible reason for the scattered test results. Fig.6 illustrates the large deflection effect by plotting L/D curves from the residual property tests for the B=1 plates after 10^5 cycles at different L_{max} . The curve of the monotonic test is superposed for comparison. Apart from the differences between these curves in the region where the deflection is within the thickness of the plate, there is no clear indication of differences between them in the final parts of the curves. Comparing to the monotonic test curve, no kinks can be seen in any residual curves unless the loading level exceeds the L_{max} of the previous fatigue. The kinks are related to the sudden occurrence or progress of damage during loading. Since the damage state is irreversible, after the first few cycles no more sudden occurrence of damage is expected until the load level exceeds the previous maximum load.

The clear reduction of the residual initial effective stiffness with increase of cycles can be seen in Fig.7 for all three aspect ratio plates after low load level fatigue. The difference between plates with B=2 and 3 is relatively small, as seen in the static tests and $L/\log N$ curves. The rate of the stiffness decrease of the B=1 plates is slightly higher than those of the B=2 and 3 plates, though the difference is small. However, when the fatigue maximum load rises to 50% of the UFL, this clear reduction of the residual stiffness no longer exists, especially above 10^4 cycles. An increase of the residual stiffness after large numbers of cycles at this load level has occurred erratically. This contradiction can probably be explained by the condition of the fatigued plates before the final monotonic residual property test. The unloaded plates when released from the edge clamp jigs after fatigue could have

some permanent deformation the amount of which depends on the load level and the number of cycles of previous fatigue procedures. Further deflection of the plate during the following residual property tests could be affected by this permanent deformation. The initial effective stiffness as a parameter to monitor changes of structural stiffness of plates with relatively small deflection has, therefore, lost its relevance. Since this stiffness increase with large permanent deflection of the plates can hardly be utilized in engineering applications, it has suggested as a fatigue failure criterion of the edge clamped plates at a certain permanent deflection.

Fig.6. Load-deflection curves of the residual property tests on the B=1 plates after 10^5 cycles.

Fig.7. Changes of the residual initial stiffness of the plates after fatigue at $L_{max} = 1.5kN$.

3.2.4. Assessment of Fatigue-Induced Damage

The damage condition of the specimens for the residual property tests were monitored by means of ultrasonic C-scan and X-radiography before they were subjected to the final monotonic loading. The damage mechanisms involved are mainly intraply matrix cracks and delamination, but also fibre fractures. Since the damage in the edge clamped plates could not be easily developed beyond the boundary of the all edge clamped support, the fatigue-induced damage progression in edge clamped plates more likely involved increases of the density of the matrix cracks. This large number of matrix cracks can easily interact with each other and with fractured fibres. This probably results in the permanent deflection of the plates. Fig.8a-d show damage detected by X-radiography on B=2 plates after fatigue at $L_{max} = 3.9kN$ for different number of cycles. Growth of the delamination zones and matrix crack density with fatigue can be seen clearly.

Fig.9 plots the projected damage areas of all three aspect ratio plates cycled at the same low fatigue load $L_{max} = 1.5kN$. Although the damage areas could have been restricted by the clamped supports, especially on the plates fatigued at high load levels for a large number of cycles, the growth of the fatigue-induced damage indicated by the projected damage area is very obvious for these specimens subjected to the low fatigue load level. The effect of the aspect ratio on fatigue-induced damage growth at the same fatigue loading level is very small except after a large number of cycles. This

agrees with the argument from the static loading damage assessment, of which the damage area is mostly affected by loading levels but not the geometry of the plates.

Fig.8. Damage detected by X-radiography on the B=2 plates after fatigue at $L_{max}=3.9kN$ up to a) 10^3 , b) 10^4 , c) 10^5 and d) 10^6 cycles.

Fig.9. Projected damage areas of the plates after fatigue at $L_{max}= 1.5kN$.

4. SUMMARY REMARKS

As one of the testing methods which introduce biaxial stress/strain into composite materials, biaxial bending exhibits its own advantages over other methods. Most of all, the biaxial bending test is very easy to set up. The similarity of biaxial bending to some engineering practices where panel components are employed marks the importance and necessity of the test method. However, the complexity of the biaxial bending stress distribution forces the composite plates to behave in ways which may not be easily interpreted, especially when the large deflection effect of the bent plate has to be accounted for. On completion of the experimental work on biaxial bending fatigue of the composite plates, with clamped edges and three different aspect ratios, the following conclusions can be drawn.

The aspect ratio clearly affects the performance of the plates. In the region studied, the mechanical properties decrease with increase of the aspect ratio for edge clamped plates. Various damage mechanisms, such as matrix cracks, delamination as well as fibre breakage, could occur in the edge clamped plates subjected to biaxial flexing fatigue. As a result of the total area being restricted by the edge clamps, damage development during fatigue, under relatively high load levels and large numbers of cycles, could preferentially take a form of increased density of various damage mechanisms. A permanent biaxial bent deformation of the edge clamped plate after heavy fatigue could possibly be related to interaction of the intensified damage mechanisms. The initial effective stiffness can still be a useful parameter for indicating the performance of edge clamped plates